

C5.2 Debriefing (treatment group)

Welcome to the activity on elicitation of context-aware features. This is a controlled experiment and the participation is anonymous.

There are 9 questions in this survey.

Debriefing

Please answer the following questions about the experiment execution. *

Please choose the appropriate response for each item:

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
My task in this experiment was clearly explained.	☐				
The time I received to perform my task was adequate.	☐				
My task in this experiment was easy.	☐				

Did you know the app "DorfFunk" before the experiment? *

☛ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose only one of the following:

- No
- Yes, but I never used it.
- Yes, and I am (or was) a user of it.
- Yes, and I participate (or participated) in the app development team.
- Other

With respect to the data-driven context model you received to support your activity: *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Your is

Please choose the appropriate response for each item:

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree	I did not notice the context model
The data-driven context model clearly indicated relevant contexts for the user task.	☐					
There were too much noise/meaningless information in the data-driven context model.	☐					
The data-driven context model helped me perform my activity.	☐					

Performance expectancy

Please indicate how much you agree or disagree with each of these statements: *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Your is

Please choose the appropriate response for each item:

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
I would find the data-driven context model useful in elicitation of context-aware functionalities.	☐				
Using the data-driven context model enables me to accomplish elicitation of context-aware functionalities more quickly.	☐				
Using the data-driven context model increases my productivity.	☐				

Effort expectancy

Please indicate how much you agree or disagree with each of these statements: *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Your is

Please choose the appropriate response for each item:

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
My usage of the data-driven context model would be clear and understandable.	☐				
It would be easy for me to become skillful at using the data-driven context model.	☐				
I would find the data-driven context model easy to use.	☐				
Learning to interpret the data-driven context model is easy for me.	☐				

Attitude toward using technology

Please indicate how much you agree or disagree with each of these statements: *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Your is

Please choose the appropriate response for each item:

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
Using the data-driven context model is a bad idea.	☐				
The data-driven context model makes elicitation of context-aware features more interesting.	☐				
Working with the data-driven context model is fun.	☐				
I like working with the data-driven context model.	☐				

Self-efficacy

I could elicit context-aware functionalities using the data-driven context model... *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Your is

Please choose the appropriate response for each item:

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
...if there was no one around to tell me what to do as I go.	☐				
...if I could call someone for help if I got stuck.	☐				
...if I had a lot of time to complete the job for which the data-driven context model was provided.	☐				
...if I had just the data-driven context model itself for assistance.	☐				

Anxiety

Please indicate how much you agree or disagree with each of these statements: *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Your is

Please choose the appropriate response for each item:

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
I feel apprehensive about using the data-driven context model.	☐				
I hesitate to use the data-driven context model for fear of making mistakes.	☐				
The data-driven context model is somehow intimidating to me.	☐				

FINAL

Do you have any further comments about the experiment?

Please write your answer here:

Thank you for your participation!

IMPORTANT Please keep your experience today confidential.

This experiment will be repeated soon with other people and they should not know the details in advance.

If you want to know more about this activity, and would like to see the results, please send a e-mail to rodrigo.falcao@iese.fraunhofer.de with the subject "C5.2 Feedback"

Submit your survey.

Thank you for completing this survey.